

Automated Workflow to Compute Thermal Transport Properties of Materials using TDEP

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Abstract

This work presents a computational workflow for calculating the thermal conductivity of crystals, which uses only atomic forces for a set of atomic configurations in supercells in which the atoms have been displaced from their equilibrium positions. These can be obtained in a number of ways, and we discuss here using data from Molecular Dynamics (MD) runs. This makes the method very useful, as it can use MD data generated by any interaction model, including first-principles calculations (like DFT), empirical interatomic potentials, or machine-learned potentials. The workflow is based on the Boltzmann Transport Equation, and leverages the Temperature Dependent Effective Potential (TDEP) package to compute phonons and thermal properties. The workflow autonomously extracts interatomic force constants (IFCs) using a baseline parameter setting and computes the thermal conductivity by efficiently converging the q-grid sampling of phonons, with user-tunable parameters to achieve the desired level of accuracy. We applied this approach to a diverse set of approximately 100 materials, spanning a wide range of space groups, to consider atomic systems with different degrees of complexities, anharmonicity and symmetry operations. We compared our results against theoretical predictions from other methods and experimental data, demonstrating the reliability and versatility of the workflow in assessing thermal transport properties across a broad class of materials.

I. INTRODUCTION

Understanding heat transport in materials is essential for a wide range of industrial applications, including electronics, automotive, renewable energy, and building systems. As technological complexity increases, so does the demand for accurate thermal properties characterization, which is crucial to design systems that minimize overheating, ensure operational safety, and improve energy efficiency. A key parameter governing heat transport is the thermal conductivity, which quantifies the ability of a material to conduct heat. The optimal thermal conductivity depends on the specific application: in high-performance electronics such as computer processors and semiconductor lasers, rapid heat dissipation is critical, requiring materials with high thermal conductivity. In contrast, applications such as thermal

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barrier coatings or thermoelectric devices benefit from low thermal conductivity to restrict heat flow and maintain thermal gradients, thus improving overall performance. To measure the thermal transport properties, a wide range of experimental techniques have been developed and widely adopted. Methods such as time-domain thermoreflectance (TDTR), laser flash analysis, 3-Omega method, or Raman thermometry are commonly employed to measure thermal conductivity and related parameters in a different range of materials, from bulk solids to thin films [1–4]. These techniques provide invaluable insight into the thermal behavior of materials on different length scales and temperature regimes. However, despite their accuracy and reliability, experimental methods can be time-consuming, resource-intensive, and sometimes limited in their applicability to complex or nanoscale systems. As a result, there is growing interest in complementing or replacing experimental approaches with computational modeling [5], which offers a more scalable, cost-effective, and versatile framework for predicting and analyzing thermal transport in advanced materials and devices. Computational modeling also allows for the discovery of materials that have not yet been synthesized, or the proposition of those on which experimental efforts should be focused.

Computational modeling of heat transport spans multiple scales and levels of physical detail, from atomistic simulations to continuum theories. The approaches vary significantly in their complexity and computational cost. In semiconductors and many dielectric materials, the lattice contribution to thermal conductivity dominates, making it the primary focus of atomistic simulation techniques.

At the atomic scale, molecular dynamics (MD) simulations have emerged as a powerful tool for studying thermal transport. Among MD-based approaches, the Green–Kubo method is widely used to calculate thermal conductivity by analyzing equilibrium heat current fluctuations, based on linear response theory. This method is particularly suitable for bulk materials and isotropic systems, although it requires long simulations to obtain statistically converged results. Another widely used MD technique is the direct (non-equilibrium) method, where a temperature gradient is imposed, and the resulting heat flux is measured directly. This method is specially suited for studying nanostructured materials, where nanostructures can be incorporated explicitly into the structural model. However, it requires very large simulation cells, both for homogeneous and nanostructured samples. For the former case, one needs to make sure of removing finite-size effects stemming from the finite length of the supercell, which can be very important as thermal conductivity is often dominated by

low-frequency, long-wavelength phonons. For the latter, the supercell must be large enough to incorporate the nanoscale features (nanoparticle size, interfaces, defect distribution, etc.) in the structural model. Additionally, very long dynamic runs are required to allow for the heat flux to be established. Both factors make these methods quite costly in practice.

In addition to being computationally costly, approaches based on MD present a fundamental limitation, as they do not account for quantum effects, restricting their validity to temperatures above the Debye temperature.

A major alternative to MD-based methods relies on the semiclassical approximations for phonon transport provided by the Boltzmann Transport Equation (BTE), which explicitly models phonon transport and scattering mechanisms such as anharmonic interactions, defects, and others. BTE approaches provide improved physical accuracy over classical dynamics approaches, but require detailed knowledge of phonon properties, the analysis and quantification of the scattering mechanisms, and the implementation of the solution to the BTE. In addition to capturing quantum effects, an advantage of BTE is that it uses the crystal periodicity, allowing to reduce the size of the simulation cell to the primitive cell and translating the workload to reciprocal space. Therefore, careful numerical convergence with respect to Brillouin zone sampling is required.

In the context of the BTE, it should be noted here that describing transport in non-periodic or disordered systems requires different theoretical tools. Early work [6, 7] extended classical correlation-based techniques to such systems, providing a foundation for studying thermal transport beyond the crystalline order. More recently, important advance has been made in unifying frameworks that reformulate the Green–Kubo approach using quantum energy flux operators, providing a unified approach and enabling rigorous calculations across both ordered and disordered materials [8, 9].

In this work, we focus on exploring heat conduction in crystalline systems using the BTE method. Several computational codes have been developed for this purpose over the years (some of them including the electron transport phenomena) [10–17]. Many of these tools are accessible as open-source software, which facilitates the adoption of the BTE approach by a broader community of researchers.

Interfacing external codes with BTE engines (for instance, to provide interatomic forces from which the harmonic and anharmonic properties can be obtained to feed the BTE calculation) would be extremely useful. This would allow to decouple the calculation of

the quantities relevant for thermal conduction (phonons, phonon-phonon interactions, etc.) from the solution of Boltzmann's transport equations. The former could then be done using any method of choice that can produce energies and forces in materials, including first-principles approaches such as Density Functional Theory (DFT) [18, 19] or more accurate methods, empirical interatomic potentials [20], or Machine-Learning interatomic potentials [21]. These materials-dependent data would then feed into the BTE to extract thermal properties such as conductivity.

The scheme drafted above would allow great flexibility for the choice of the method to provide materials-dependent forces, while encapsulating the transport equation into a general-purpose computational tool. Although conceptually simple, the actual realization of this scheme is much more involved. The information necessary to carry out the BTE calculations includes the phonon structure (frequencies and eigenmodes as a function of momentum), and the phonon-phonon interactions (or other phonon decay mechanisms to be considered, such as defect scattering, isotopic disorder, or others). These quantities are usually not readily computed by the codes that do provide energies and forces, although they can be obtained from these basic properties. Orchestrating the calculation of phonon properties from external force calculation engines is done by some of the BTE methods mentioned above [12, 17]. This approach is of great interest as it can transform any code able to produce forces for specific structures into an engine to obtain thermal properties of materials.

The purpose of this paper is to describe a set of tools to automate the calculation of thermal properties from any force engine, using the TDEP method [17, 22, 23] and package [24]. TDEP is designed to obtain the phonon structure and the phonon-phonon interactions from snapshots of the crystal structure in which the atoms in a supercell have been displaced from their equilibrium positions. By using a sufficiently large number of displacement configurations and the atomic forces on each of them, all the interatomic force constants (harmonic and higher order) needed to calculate the phonons and their interactions can be obtained. These are then fed into a BTE, also available in the TDEP package. TDEP is designed to obtain the phonon structure and the phonon-phonon interactions from snapshots of the crystal structure in which the atoms in a supercell have been displaced from their equilibrium positions. By using a sufficiently large number of displacement configurations and the atomic forces on each of them, all the interatomic force constants (harmonic and higher

order) needed to calculate the phonons and their interactions can be obtained. These are then fed into a BTE, also available in the TDEP package. The code used to obtain the atomic forces is therefore just an external engine which is called for a number of snapshots, making the approach very general and able to compute thermal properties from any method or code that provides atomic forces.

The paper describes our workflows developed to automate these calculations along the lines described in the previous paragraph. In particular, we use TDEP as the package to (i) generate the displacement configurations, (ii) obtain the harmonic and anharmonic force constants from the atomic forces for these configurations (obtained by an external force engine), (iii) obtain the phonons and phonon-phonon interactions, and (iv) solve the Boltzmann transport equations to obtain the thermal conductivity. Our python workflows orchestrate all these steps involving TDEP, and also the calls to the external engine used to obtain forces for specific snapshots. We emphasize that the workflows are agnostic to the force engine used, as long as the appropriate format to obtain atomic forces is defined and implemented in the python scripts.

Besides describing the workflows developed, here we demonstrate them for a pilot case. Our demonstration consists of MD trajectories and forces obtained from DFT calculations using the VASP code [25], for a set of 93 crystalline materials. This demonstration case therefore does not use the capacity of TDEP to generate the snapshots, but uses trajectories of MD runs obtained by the external force calculation engine (VASP in this case), using its own Molecular Dynamics capabilities. This demonstration case is especially important in practice, as it represents a common situation in which MD trajectories have been already generated, which can then be readily used to obtain the thermal properties of the material through the BTE formulation. For validation purposes, we compare the results for the thermal conductivities for the materials considered with experiment and with previous theoretical calculations [26] for those cases in which these are available.

II. METHODOLOGY: THE COMPUTATIONAL WORKFLOW

The workflow described in this work is based on the Temperature Dependent Effective Potential (TDEP) method [17, 22, 23]. TDEP extracts interatomic force constants (IFCs) that inherently account for finite-temperature effects. This makes TDEP particularly well

suited for the calculation of thermal conductivity because it provides temperature-dependent IFCs and anharmonic couplings obtained from atomic configurations and forces sampled at the temperature of interest. The core principle involves performing molecular dynamics (MD) simulations or using atomic configurations stochastically drawn from the canonical distribution [27, 28] at the target temperature and applying a least-squares fitting procedure to map atomic forces onto an effective hamiltonian with harmonic and higher-order interatomic interactions. Unlike standard perturbative methods, TDEP explicitly captures anharmonic effects and the renormalization of vibrational modes at finite temperatures. Therefore, TDEP is especially useful for investigating materials with strong anharmonicity or dynamical instabilities - situations where conventional zero-temperature perturbative approaches become unreliable. Consequently, it has become an essential tool for the study of thermoelectrics, phase-change materials, and compounds characterized by soft phonon modes.

This workflow combines the flexibility in choosing the method to compute the atomic forces with the efficiency of the TDEP approach for obtaining the IFCs, and its lattice dynamics and transport solvers, providing a robust framework for investigating thermal transport in complex materials. A key advantage of this approach is that it requires only atomic coordinates and forces as input regardless of their origin. While in this particular work we demonstrate the method using ab initio forces from *Ab Initio* Molecular Dynamics (AIMD) simulations, the workflow is fundamentally force-field agnostic. This universality means it can integrate forces derived from classical potentials, machine-learning interatomic potentials, DFT, or any other atomistic modeling tool, making it broadly applicable across a wide range of materials modeling scenarios.

Here we give a brief account of the technical details of our workflow. It is written in python, and is available in Gitlab [29] as part of the *teff-py* package of workflows involving the SIESTA materials simulation code and TDEP:

- The *teff-md-workflow*: (*MD-TDEP*, which is the focus of the present report) constructs the TDEP effective hamiltonian using the positions-forces information from a molecular dynamics (MD) run at a certain temperature. The MD data can be produced by any code (first-principles or otherwise). The workflow can then compute the phonon dispersion relations and the thermal conductivity.

- The *teff-scha-workflow*: (*sTDEP*), drives the DFT code SIESTA as a force calculator, while wrapped utilities from the TDEP suite provide canonically-distributed snapshot structures and calculate resulting properties (phonon dispersion, thermal conductivity). The two codes operate in a cycle, refining the effective Hamiltonian of the physical system along a number of iterations (with increasing number of structural snapshots, until the studied properties reach specified convergence criteria. This workflow is currently SIESTA-specific, but its architecture would enable the use of any other simulation code (again, first-principles or otherwise) as backend with minor changes.

The workflow relies heavily on the plumbum shell combinators library [30], which allows to build thin wrappers over the TDEP command-line utilities. Orchestration is performed by a lightweight workflow mechanism defined in `teff_py.actions`. The mechanism represents the *Command Software Pattern* [31] for execution of local shell commands and can be reused for building similar command chains. A useful feature of this mechanism is that the calculations are encapsulated in such a way that they are executed only once for given parameters. This saves computational time and helps maintain a cache of results in the filesystem during analysis and convergence studies.

The *MD-TDEP* workflow requires a set of files in a specific format (which can be generated by converting the output of any suitable code), containing information about:

- The unit-cell of the material.
- The supercell used in the MD simulation.
- A time-series of atomic positions.
- A time-series of the corresponding forces.
- Metadata on temperature, number of MD steps, etc.

In addition, extra operational parameters are specified in a configuration file in YAML format: `md_config.yaml`:

- The stride for sampling the MD files.
- The range cutoffs for the interatomic force constants.
- The minimum and maximum densities of the q-points for the computation of the thermal conductivity. Typically, the thermal conductivity is computed for various values of this parameter until convergence (determined by relative change being smaller than a given tolerance) is reached.

- A tolerance for the convergence of the thermal conductivity.

The workflow can compute phonon dispersion relations and the thermal conductivity by wrapping the corresponding command-line utilities of TDEP, automatically taking care of passing the parameters and performing the needed steps in the appropriate order, taking advantage of the plumbum caching mechanism mentioned above.

The general steps involved in the operation of the *MD-TDEP* workflow are the following:

1. **Initial Dataset Preparation:** The workflow needs a dataset consisting of atomic coordinates and the corresponding forces acting on each atom. These can be obtained from a variety of sources, including molecular dynamics (MD) trajectories generated using classical force fields, machine-learning potentials, or first-principles calculations. The methodology is agnostic to the origin of the data, making it widely applicable across computational materials modeling approaches. It could also analyze data obtained in the different steps of the *sTDEP* workflow.
2. **Force Constant Extraction:** The time series of coordinates and forces is used to extract temperature-dependent interatomic force constants (IFCs), which are used to build an effective Hamiltonian (harmonic and higher-order) through a least-squares fitting procedure. The workflow allows users to specify the cutoff radii for both second-order and third-order IFCs, denoted r_{c2} and r_{c3} , respectively. These values determine the spatial range of interactions included in the model and are user-defined parameters that can be tuned to study the convergence of the computed thermal conductivity. The maximum possible range of IFCs is imposed by the size of the simulation supercell; specifically, interaction distances cannot exceed half the supercell length in any direction. Larger supercells allow for longer-range interactions to be included. However, choosing the maximum possible cutoff is not always necessary as a matter of balance between accuracy and cost, and convergence tests of the supercell size and the cutoff radii are advised to determine optimal values to maximize efficiency.
3. **Thermal Conductivity Calculation:** Using the extracted IFCs, the lattice thermal conductivity is computed by solving the phonon Boltzmann Transport Equation (BTE). The workflow incrementally increases the density of the q -point mesh used to sample the phonons across the Brillouin zone until the thermal conductivity converges

FIG. 1. Distribution of materials analyzed categorized by their space groups.

within a user-defined tolerance (e.g., 5%). This automated convergence procedure ensures accurate and consistent results across different systems.

III. VALIDATION OF THE WORKFLOW

In this study, we apply the above workflow to a dataset obtained from AIMD simulations previously performed by Florian Knoop [26, 32] using VASP [25] for 93 different crystalline materials, spanning nine different space groups and exhibiting a broad range of unit cell sizes and anharmonic behavior. This diversity enables a robust assessment of our workflow’s effectiveness and generality across structurally varied systems. Figure 1 shows the distribution of materials in our dataset according to their crystallographic symmetries.

The MD simulations were run at a temperature of 300 K, using a timestep of 1 fs in supercells of approximately 200 atoms, constructed in accordance with the space-group symmetries of each of the materials under investigation. We used 750 consecutive snapshots of each molecular dynamics simulation, passing the atomic positions and forces of each snapshot to TDEP to calculate the IFCs. These were used to compute the thermal conductivity (at 300 K) through the solution of the Boltzmann Transport Equation. In this work, we

consider phonon-phonon interactions only from third-order anharmonic terms in the IFCs. Higher order terms could be included in the calculation of the conductivity, as TDEP allows to consider the fourth order terms [33]. All our calculations include isotope scattering in the thermal conductivity, using the model of Tamura [34] and tabulated values of the natural isotope occurrence (both available and implemented in the TDEP code).

Although we only consider one temperature in this validation study, we note here that the calculation of the thermal conductivity for different temperatures would involve generating a separate dataset of coordinates and forces for each target temperature. However, it is often sufficient to use IFCs obtained at one temperature (e.g., 300 K) to approximate the thermal conductivity at nearby temperatures. This approximation becomes less accurate as the target temperature deviates significantly from the sampling temperature, and its validity should be evaluated based on the degree of anharmonicity in the system under study.

The specific choice of convergence parameters in this study is intended to serve as a proof of concept rather than a rigorous convergence study. Our primary objective is to assess the reliability and robustness of the proposed workflow, and to compare our results with existing published results from calculations and from experiment. Although it is possible to fine-tune our computational parameters using heuristic approaches or advanced optimisation strategies to improve accuracy, such refinement falls outside the scope of the current work. The focus here is on demonstrating the general applicability and effectiveness of the workflow, rather than achieving the absolute best numerical precision. More specifically:

- The cutoff radius for second-order interactions (r_{c2}) was set equal half the length of the supercell, which is the largest possible value for that given supercell.
- The third-order interactions (r_{c3}) were truncated at two-thirds of the maximum interaction range (which, again, is half the length of the supercell) However, we will also present examples of the results obtained for some materials when r_{c3} was increased systematically to assess convergence.
- The q -point mesh density was refined iteratively until the change in calculated thermal conductivity between successive refinements was below 5%.

To evaluate our results, which are summarized in Appendix I, II, the computed thermal conductivity values obtained are compared against experimental data from the literature

FIG. 2. Comparison of the conductivities computed in this work and the experimental ones. See Table II for references for experimental data). The color of each point indicates the space group number, according to Fig. 1. The broken line indicates perfect agreement.

and theoretical results obtained via the Green-Kubo method and DFT, also using the VASP code [26]. Fig. 2, shows the comparison between our predicted thermal conductivity values and experimental data for those materials in our dataset for which they are available. To quantitatively assess our results, we compute several standard statistical metrics, including the R^2 score, root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and mean bias.

FIG. 3. Comparison of the conductivities computed in this work and Green-Kubo calculations from ref. 26. The color of each point indicates the space group number, according to Fig. 1. The broken line indicates perfect agreement.

The first column of Table I shows the correlations between our calculations and the experimental values. The value of R^2 indicates a strong correlation between the results of our validation exercise and experimental data: our results capture nearly 80% of the variance in the experimental results. While not perfect, this level of agreement is noteworthy given the complexity of the processes and the approximations made in the calculation of the thermal

FIG. 4. Comparison of the conductivities from the Green-Kubo calculations in ref. 26 and the experimental ones. See Table II for references for experimental data). The color of each point indicates the space group number, according to Fig. 1. The broken line indicates perfect agreement.

conductivity, and the inherent variability in experimental results, obtained from different works and with different techniques. The RMSE and MAE (7.8 W/m·K and 4.6 W/m·K, respectively) show that the average deviations are around 5 W/m·K, but with some cases being significantly larger. We observe a positive mean bias of +1.7 W/m·K, indicating a systematic overestimation of thermal conductivity. The results of our validation exercise tend

TABLE I. Correlation between the three sets of conductivity data: this work (TW), experiment (Exp) and Green-Kubo (GK) from [26].

Metric	TW/Exp	TW/GK	GK/Exp
R^2	0.79	0.56	0.86
RMSE (W/m·K)	7.83	7.01	4.79
MAE (W/m·K)	4.60	4.07	3.08
Mean Bias (W/m·K)	1.71	3.60	-0.73

to slightly overestimate the conductivities compared to experiment. One possible explanation is the limited size of the supercell used to compute the atomic forces, which imposes a limited range for the 2nd and 3rd order interatomic force constants (IFCs); the former may limit the accuracy of the computed phonons frequencies and displacements, while the second may not capture all relevant third-order anharmonic interactions, which would lead to an overestimation of the conductivity. The same occurs as a result of the neglect of fourth-order IFCs. Below we will explore the effect of increasing the value of the r_{c3} on the values of the conductivity obtained.

Fig. 3 shows the comparison of the results of our calculations and those of the Green-Kubo approach from Ref. 26. In comparing our results with the Green-Kubo ones, we should note that both calculation are based on DFT, and done with the same code (VASP) and approximations (pseudopotentials, DFT functional, etc.). Therefore, differences between both calculations cannot be ascribed to the model to obtain the MD trajectories, energies and atomic forces, but rather to the method of calculation of the thermal conductivity. We observe a systematic tendency of the BTE results to produce larger conductivities than the GK approach. As shown in Fig. 4, the Green-Kubo formulation seems to underestimate systematically the conductivities compared to the experimental results, contrary to our observations with the BTE equation, which overestimates them. This is also observed in the third column of Table I, which shows a negative mean bias of the GK results with respect to experiment. A detailed study of the origin of these differences between BTE and GK results is out of the scope of this work, and will be presented elsewhere.

As discussed above, the accuracy of our calculations can be improved by extending the

range used for the third-order IFC calculations. By considering a larger interaction range, we account for increased anharmonicity, capturing more accurately possible phonon scattering mechanisms, and providing more accurate thermal conductivity predictions. In this study, we repeated the calculations varying the 3rd order IFC ranges for a selection of compounds, until reaching the maximum value allowed by the size of the supercell used in MD run. The results are presented in the left panels of Figures 5 and 6. Except for very short values of r_{c3} (smaller than 4 Å), the computed conductivity values do not change much with the cutoff of the third-order IFCs. Increasing r_{c3} produces an increase of the conductivity for some materials, and a decrease in others. Nevertheless, the changes are of just a few percent.

We have done a similar procedure to study the convergence of the conductivity as a function of the density of q-points used for the phonons in the BTE. The results are shown in the right panels of Figures 5 and 6. We see that the effect of the q-grid density is larger than that of r_{c3} , which justifies our approach that it is the workflow that takes care of finding a converged value setting a tolerance for the change of the conductivity calculated.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we developed and validated a robust computational workflow for predicting lattice thermal conductivity using trajectories and forces from molecular dynamics simulations. The workflow leverages the Temperature Dependent Effective Potential (TDEP) method to extract second- and third-order IFCs from MD data and to solve the Boltzmann Transport Equation to compute temperature-dependent thermal conductivity. A key strength of the workflow lies in its flexibility: all steps are controlled through a YAML input file, allowing users to specify the desired accuracy and computational settings, including the q-grid sampling, target temperature, cutoff radii and others.

Our validation study has demonstrated the capacity of our workflow to compute thermal conductivities of materials using only as an input the snapshots of coordinates and forces obtained from an external simulation code. Our case study involved MD data for 93 materials obtained from DFT calculations done with the VASP code, but our workflow is agnostic to the source of the MD data, and can use input from any method or simulation code, be it first-principles, empirical potentials, or machine-learning potentials. This makes the method broadly useful and easily adaptable within existing simulation pipelines. Its ability to provide

FIG. 5. Variation of the conductivity κ_{xx} with the third-order IFCs range r_{c3} , in the left panels, and nq , the number of grid points in each direction for the phonon in reciprocal space (input variable `--qpoint_grid` in TDEP), in the right panels, for a selected group of compounds with space groups 166, 186 and 216. The vertical lines in the left panel indicates the default value of r_{c3} for each compound (defined as two-thirds of the maximum allowed by the supercell size).

FIG. 6. Dependence of the conductivity κ_{xx} on the third-order IFCs range r_{c3} , in the left panels, and nq , the number of grid points in each direction for the phonon in reciprocal space (input variable `--qpoint_grid` in TDEP), in the right panels, for a selected group of compounds with space group 225. The vertical lines in the left panel indicates the default value of r_{c3} for each compound (defined as two-thirds of the maximum allowed by the supercell size).

accurate thermal transport properties from diverse MD datasets gives it universal utility, particularly in scenarios where conventional lattice dynamics techniques become unreliable, such as in highly anharmonic, disordered, or temperature-dependent systems.

Overall, this study confirms the effectiveness of combining molecular dynamics, automated IFC extraction, and adaptive q-grid refinement within a single, user-friendly workflow. It provides a scalable and accurate tool for investigating phonon transport in a wide range

of crystalline materials, paving the way for high-throughput thermal property screening in material discovery.

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Appendix A: Thermal Conductivity Results

TABLE II: Thermal conductivity results , compared to the Green-Kubo calculations of Ref. [26] and experimental data.

Material	Space Group	Thermal conductivity (W/m/K)	Green-Kubo [[26]]	Experiment [Ref.]
SnSe	062	0.94		1 [35]
KCaF3	062	1.96	2	1.06 [36]
AgAlS2	122	1.67	1.01	
AgGaSe2	122	1.12	0.61	1 [37]
GaLiTe2	122	3.45	0.81	
AlCuSe2	122	5.49		
AlCuS2	122	7.18		
CuInS2	122	11.63		
InLiTe2	122	4.24	1.01	
AgAlSe2	122	0.99	0.62	
AlLiTe2	122	4.30		
AgAlTe2	122	2.25		
Ba2ClP	166	3.65		
InNaS2	166	3.46	2.22	
CuScO2	166	28.21		
InNaSe2	166	2.43		
LiRhO2	166	30.36	13.37	
Ba2BrN	166	1.96		
LiScS2	166	10.57	6.42	
InNaO2	166	11.76	9.71	
Sr2HN	166	7.60	4.17	
Sr2ClN	166	5.32		
InLiSe2	166	2.30	2.34	
CuGaO2	166	42.27	12.82	
Sr2IN	166	3.16		
ZnTe	216	25.85		10.8 [38]
InAs	216	26.03		27 [39]
CuBr	216	0.53		1.25[40]
AlAs	216	69.92		84 [41]
GaAs	216	36.77		55 [42, 43]

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Material	Space Group	Thermal conductivity (W/m/K)	Green-Kubo [[26]]	Experiment [Ref.]
CuCl	216	0.87	0.49	0.84 [44]
CdS	216	20.93		20 [45]
ZnSe	216	19.95		18 [46]
CuI	216	7.40	1.38	1.68[47]
CdTe	216	8.23		5.9 [48]
ZnS	216	53.63		25.1 [46]
LiAsMg	216	10.59	4.67	
LiAsZn	216	7.91		
LiNZn	216	18.03	8.42	
ZnPLi	216	13.38	2.09	
RbZnF3	221	3.45	3.47	
RbMgF3	221	6.12	6.94	
SrTiO3	221	10.78		
CsCdF3	221	2.33	2.3	
CsCaF3	221	4.74		
BaLiF3	221	3.61	3.27	
KMgF3	221	11.27	10.08	10[49]
KZnF3	221	4.97	4.7	5.5 [50]
LiF	225	17.81	13.78	17.6 [51]
BaO	225	4.92	3.09	2.3 [51]
CaTe	225	10.70		
RbF	225	2.66	2.27	2.26 [52]
BaS	225	6.07		
KBr	225	3.04		4.82 [53]
LiI	225	3.35	1.07	
RbI	225	2.53		9.9 [54]
BaSe	225	12.70		
LiCl	225	5.03	4.14	
NaBr	225	3.35	2.35	2.8 [55]
CsF	225	1.79	0.84	
SrO	225	11.41	5.98	10 [51]
NaF	225	36.26	14.03	16.5 [51]
KF	225	8.87	4.38	6.43 [51]
AgCl	225	0.77	0.5	

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Table continued from previous page

Material	Space Group	Thermal conductivity (W/m/K)	Green-Kubo [[26]]	Experiment [Ref.]
SrTe	225	12.31		
KH	225	8.43	3.39	
KI	225	2.21		
BaTe	225	11.59		
RbCl	225	2.65		
MgO	225	58.87	67.84	61 [56]
CaO	225	30.97	28.95	27[51]
KCl	225	11.11		6.53 [57]
LiBr	225	3.38	1.6	
RbBr	225	5.82		3.38
NaCl	225	10.32	6.66	7.1 [58]
LiH	225	21.37	23.56	14.7 [59]
AgBr	225	0.71		1.21 [60]
SrS	225	12.52		10.7 [61]
Na ₂ S	225	8.23	4.4	
CaF ₂	225	12.09	7.61	9.71 [62]
Rb ₂ O	225	3.39	2.08	
Li ₂ Se	225	11.89	4.55	17.7 [63]
Li ₂ O	225	21.89	21.39	15 [64]
SrF ₂	225	13.15		10 [65]
CdF ₂	225	5.23	2.24	4.3 [66]
K ₂ S	225	4.03		
Na ₂ Te	225	4.72	1.64	
Li ₂ Te	225	8.97	3.24	14.7 [63]
K ₂ Te	225	3.17		
Rb ₂ Se	225	2.12		
Li ₂ S	225	16.83	13.85	
Na ₂ Se	225	6.92	2.63	
K ₂ O	225	4.80	3.67	2.5 [64]

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- [1] W. J. Parker, R. J. Jenkins, C. P. Butler, and G. L. Abbott, Flash method of determining thermal diffusivity, heat capacity, and thermal conductivity, *Journal of Applied Physics* **32**, 1679 (1961).
- [2] D. G. Cahill, Thermal conductivity measurement from 30 to 750K: The 3ω method, *Review of Scientific Instruments* **61**, 802 (1990).
- [3] A. A. Balandin, Thermal properties of graphene and nanostructured carbon materials, *Nature Materials* **10**, 569 (2008).
- [4] D. G. Cahill, K. Goodson, and A. Majumdar, Thermometry and thermal transport in micro/nanoscale solid-state devices and structures, *Journal of Heat Transfer* **124**, 223 (2001).
- [5] L. Lach and D. Svyetlichnyy, Advances in numerical modeling for heat transfer and thermal management: A review of computational approaches and environmental impacts, *Energies* **18**, 1302 (2025).
- [6] P. Allen and J. Feldman, Thermal conductivity of glasses: theory and application to amorphous Si, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **62**, 645 (1989).
- [7] P. Allen and J. Feldman, Thermal conductivity of disordered harmonic solids, *Phys. Rev. B.* **48**, 12581 (1993).
- [8] M. Simoncelli, N. Marzari, and F. Mauri, Wigner formulation of thermal transport in solids, *Phys. Rev. X* **12**, 041011 (2022).
- [9] L. Isaeva, G. Barbalinardo, D. Donadio, and S. Baroni, Modeling heat transport in crystals and glasses from a unified lattice-dynamical approach, *Nature Communications* **10**, 3853 (2019).
- [10] D. A. Broido, M. Malorny, G. Birner, N. Mingo, and D. A. Stewart, Intrinsic lattice thermal conductivity of semiconductors from 1st principles, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **91**, 231922 (2007).
- [11] W. Li, J. Carrete, N. A. Katcho, and N. Mingo, ShengBTE: a solver of the Boltzmann transport equation for phonons, *Comput. Phys. Commun.* **185**, 1747 (2014).
- [12] A. Togo, L. Chaput, and I. Tanaka, Distributions of phonon lifetimes in brillouin zones, *Phys. Rev. B* **91**, 094306 (2015).
- [13] S. Ponce, E. R. Margine, C. Verdi, and F. Giustino, EPW: electron–phonon coupling, transport and superconducting properties using maximally localized Wannier functions, *Comput. Phys. Commun.* **209**, 116 (2016).

- [14] J.-J. Zhou, J. Park, I.-T. Lu, I. Maliyov, X. Tong, and M. Bernardi, Perturbo: a software package for ab initio electron–phonon interactions, charge transport and ultrafast dynamics, *Comput. Phys. Commun.* **264**, 107970 (2021).
- [15] N. H. Protik, C. Li, M. Pruneda, B. David, and P. Ordejón, The elphbolt ab initio solver for the coupled electron-phonon Boltzmann transport equations, *npj Computational Materials* **8**, 28 (2022).
- [16] A. Cepellotti, J. Coulter, A. Johansson, N. S. Fedorova, and B. Kozinsky, Phoebe: a high-performance framework for solving phonon and electron boltzmann transport equations, *Journal of Physics: Materials* **5**, 035003 (2022).
- [17] F. Knoop, N. Shulumba, A. Castellano, J. P. A. Batista, R. Farris, M. J. Verstraete, M. Heine, D. Broido, D. S. Kim, J. Klarbring, I. A. Abrikosov, S. I. Simak, and O. Hellman, TDEP: Temperature dependent effective potentials, *Journal of Open Source Software* **9**, 6150 (2024).
- [18] P. Hohenberg and W. Kohn, *Phys. Rev.* **136**, 864 (1964).
- [19] W. Kohn and L. J. Sham, *Phys. Rev.* **137**, 1697 (1965).
- [20] D. Brenner, The art and science of an analytic potential, *physica status solidi (b)* **217**, 23 (2000).
- [21] R. Jacobs, D. Morgan, S. Attarian, J. Meng, C. Shen, Z. Wu, C. Y. Xie, J. H. Yang, N. Artrith, B. Blaiszik, G. Ceder, K. Choudhary, G. Csanyi, E. D. Cubuk, B. Deng, R. Drautz, X. Fu, J. Godwin, V. Honavar, O. Isayev, A. Johansson, B. Kozinsky, S. Martiniani, S. P. Ong, I. Poltavsky, K. Schmidt, S. Takamoto, A. P. Thompson, J. Westermayr, and B. M. Wood, A practical guide to machine learning interatomic potentials – status and future, *Current Opinion in Solid State and Materials Science* **35**, 101214 (2025).
- [22] O. Hellman and D. Broido, Phonon thermal transport in Bi_2O_3 from first principles, *Phys. Rev. B* **90**, 134309 (2014).
- [23] A. Castellano, J. P. A. Batista, O. Hellman, and M. J. Verstraete, Mode-coupling formulation of heat transport in anharmonic materials, *Phys. Rev. B* **111**, 094306 (2025).
- [24] <https://tdep-developers.github.io/tdep>.
- [25] G. Kresse and J. Furthmüller, Efficient iterative schemes for ab initio total-energy calculations using a plane-wave basis set, *Physical Review B* **54**, 11169 (1996).
- [26] F. Knoop, T. A. R. Purcell, M. Scheffler, and C. Carbogno, Anharmonicity in thermal insulators: An analysis from first principles, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **130**, 236301 (2023).

- [27] D. West and S. K. Estreicher, First-principles calculations of vibrational lifetimes and decay channels: Hydrogen-related modes in Si, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **96**, 115504 (2006).
- [28] N. Shulumba, O. Hellman, and A. J. Minnich, Lattice thermal conductivity of polyethylene molecular crystals from first-principles including nuclear quantum effects, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **119**, 185901 (2017).
- [29] <https://gitlab.com/siesta-project/ecosystem/teff-py>.
- [30] <https://plumbum.readthedocs.io/>.
- [31] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Command_pattern.
- [32] F. Knoop, Private Communication.
- [33] J. Klarbring, O. Hellman, I. A. Abrikosov, and S. I. Simak, Anharmonicity and ultralow thermal conductivity in lead-free halide double perovskites, *Phys. Rev. Lett* **125**, 045701 (2020).
- [34] S.-i. Tamura, Isotope scattering of dispersive phonons in ge, *Phys. Rev. B* **27**, 858 (1983).
- [35] L. D. Zhao, S. H. Lo, Y. Zhang, *et al.*, Ultralow thermal conductivity and high thermoelectric figure of merit in sncs crystals, *Nature* **508**, 373 (2014).
- [36] A. Ali, A. U. Rahman, and G. Rahman, Thermoelectric properties of kcaF₃, *Physica B: Condensed Matter* **565**, 18 (2019).
- [37] J. D. Beasley, Thermal conductivities of some novel nonlinear optical materials, *Applied Optics* **33**, 1000 (1994).
- [38] MatWeb LLC, Material properties for znTe, https://www.matweb.com/search/datasheet_print.aspx?matguid=9ddc8b3e9c0c45d9ad5c2eb346b93802 ().
- [39] J. Rumble, ed., *CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics*, 105th ed. (CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, 2024).
- [40] MatWeb LLC, Material properties for CuBr, <https://www.matweb.com/search/DataSheet.aspx?MatGUID=d6be1ba2e6584fd8bc2dd69f4aabd3ff&ckck=1> ().
- [41] MatWeb LLC, Material properties for AlAs, <https://www.matweb.com/search/DataSheet.aspx?MatGUID=f22d9c7bc84c40a18be8f2f5db46383c> ().
- [42] Jet Propulsion Laboratory, I. GaAs material properties, <https://parts.jpl.nasa.gov/mmhc/3-I.PDF>.
- [43] S. Wemple, Thermal design of power GaAs, in *GaAs FET Principles and Technology*, edited by J. DiLorenzo (Artech House, Dedham, MA, 1982).

- [44] MatWeb LLC, Material properties for cucl, <https://www.matweb.com/search/DataSheet.aspx?MatGUID=b060755efb9a43ddb50a0292171d05b2&ckck=1> ().
- [45] MatWeb LLC, Material properties for cds, <https://www.matweb.com/search/DataSheet.aspx?MatGUID=b583d875400c4b4da69024fea50a18d3> ().
- [46] MatWeb LLC, Material properties for zns, https://www.matweb.com/search/datasheet_print.aspx?matguid=c83ec9da11354180899be8684ccb5228 ().
- [47] MatWeb LLC, Material properties for cui, <https://www.matweb.com/search/DataSheet.aspx?MatGUID=65f7fee1d4eb47dd944e44241504b7ad> ().
- [48] MatWeb LLC, Material properties for cdte, <https://www.matweb.com/search/DataSheet.aspx?MatGUID=3f3bbec8a6664fc3963fe8d79adc2622> ().
- [49] J. J. Martin, G. S. Dixon, and P. P. Velasco, Phonon scattering in rbcaf₃ and kmnf₃, *Phys. Rev. B* **14**, 2609 (1976).
- [50] Y. Suemune and H. Ikawa, *Journal of the Physical Society of Japan* **19**, 1686 (1964).
- [51] D. T. Morelli and G. A. Slack, High lattice thermal conductivity solids, in *High Thermal Conductivity Materials*, edited by S. L. Shindé and J. S. Goela (Springer New York, New York, NY, 2006) pp. 37–68.
- [52] B. Hakansson and R. G. Ross, Thermal conductivity and heat capacity of solid libr and rbf under pressure, *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter* **1**, 3977 (1989).
- [53] Lakeshore Optical Materials, Potassium bromide (kbr) transmission curve datasheet, PDF file, Lakeshore Optical Materials (n.d.).
- [54] Crystran Ltd, Rubidium iodide (rbi) optical material, <https://www.crystran.com/optical-materials/rubidium-iodide-rbi> (2025), accessed: 2025-08-14.
- [55] I. Sigalas, B. Håkansson, and P. Andersson, Thermal conductivity and heat capacity of solid nabr under pressure, *International Journal of Thermophysics* **6**, 177 (1985).
- [56] W. MacPherson and H. Schloessin, High temperatures, *High Temperatures. High Pressures* **15**, 495 (1983).
- [57] Crystran Ltd, Potassium chloride (kcl) optical material, <https://www.crystran.com/optical-materials/potassium-chloride-kcl> (2024), accessed: 2025-08-14.
- [58] Y. S. Touloukian, R. W. Powell, C. Y. Ho, and P. G. Klemens, *Thermophysical Properties of Matter - The TPRC Data Series. Volume 2. Thermal Conductivity - Nonmetallic Solids* (IFI/Plenum, New York, 1971).

- [59] G. A. Slack, *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids* **34**, 321 (1973).
- [60] Korth Kristalle GmbH, Silver bromide (agbr) optical material (2025).
- [61] X.-Y. Hou, Y. Cheng, C.-E. Hu, C.-G. Piao, and H.-Y. Geng, Thermoelectric properties of strontium sulfide via first-principles calculations, *Solid State Communications* **305**, 113755 (2020).
- [62] Mateck Material Technologie & Kristalle GmbH, Calcium fluoride (caf₂) optical material, <https://mateck.com/en/content/70-calcium-fluoride-caf2> (2025), accessed: 2025-08-14.
- [63] S. Mukhopadhyay, L. Lindsay, and D. S. Parker, Optic phonon bandwidth and lattice thermal conductivity: The case of li₂x (x = o, s, se, te), *Physical Review B* **93**, 224301 (2016).
- [64] A. E. Gheribi, A. Seifitokaldani, P. Wu, and P. Chartrand, An ab initio method for the prediction of the lattice thermal transport properties of oxide systems: Case study of li₂o and k₂o, *Journal of Applied Physics* **118**, 145101 (2015), https://pubs.aip.org/aip/jap/article-pdf/doi/10.1063/1.4932643/15169994/145101.1_online.pdf.
- [65] J. Moore, F. Weaver, R. Graves, and D. McElroy, in *Thermal Conductivity 18* (Springer, 1985) pp. 115–124.
- [66] P. A. Popov, P. P. Fedorov, and V. V. Osiko, Thermal conductivity of single crystals with a fluorite structure: Cadmium fluoride, *Physics of the Solid State* **52**, 504 (2010).
- [67] Crystran Ltd., Zinc selenide (znse) — properties, <https://www.crystran.com/optical-materials/zinc-selenide-znse> (2024).
- [68] L. Lindsay, First principles peierls-boltzmann phonon thermal transport: A topical review, *Nanoscale and Microscale Thermophysical Engineering* **20**, 67 (2016).
- [69] D. G. Cahill, W. K. Ford, K. E. Goodson, G. D. Mahan, A. Majumdar, H. J. Maris, R. Merlin, and S. R. Phillpot, Nanoscale thermal transport, *Journal of Applied Physics* **93**, 793 (2003).